

Evaluation Of The Mathematics Book For The First Intermediate Grade, The First Part, From The Point Of View Of Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 21, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 22, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teachers, Mathematics Book, Holy City Of Karbala</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7013819</p>	<p>Research Summary</p> <p><i>The current research aims to evaluate the mathematics book C1 for the first intermediate grade from the point of view of teachers</i></p> <p><i>Determine the current search by:</i></p> <p>1- <i>Mathematics book for the first intermediate grade, first part. Dr. Amir Abdul Majeed Jassim, d. Tariq Shaaban Rajab and others. 4th floor, General Directorate of Curricula, 2019.</i></p> <p>2- <i>Faculty members of mathematics for the first intermediate grade in middle schools in the holy city of Karbala for the academic year 2021-2022</i></p> <p><i>The research tool consisted of a questionnaire consisting of 24 items presented to a sample of experts and carried out on an exploratory sample and then implemented on the main sample consisting of 20 teachers in the field of mathematics. The result was that the book was accepted in most of its paragraphs, and their impressions were positive about it, except for paragraph (2,3).</i></p>

Introduction

Chapter one

Research importance and problem:

Education is the society's means to raise its children in accordance with the direction desired by that society, as the curriculum is the effective tool in the hands of the student and the teacher to represent the content of the educational material that embodies the desire and direction of societies in building generations.

Curricula are the precise means by which educational policies dominate the minds and the construction of thought (Al-Hashimi, 1999, p. 139). Because education is required to bring about influences and changes in the lives of societies in order for those societies to move towards progress and prosperity. Curricula are the means of education to achieve its planned goals, as the curricula provide the learner with multiple experiences that help him develop all aspects of his personality in an integrated manner. (Al-Samarrai and others, 1995, p. 9), (Al-Dayni, 1987, p. 22).

The curricula have gone through important developments and moved from the old concept of the curriculum, which emphasized the courses offered by the school to its students within its walls, in order to evaluate them at the end of the school year. The curriculum is all educational experiences that have been planned by specialized educational bodies and organized in a graduated series that takes into account the possibilities of teaching and learning and the specified time period with the aim of helping each learner to comprehensive growth in accordance with set goals and specific strategies that are closely related to the goals and strategies of society that are provided to learners under the supervision of the school and directing it in a manner that is compatible with the capabilities and capabilities of the community. Each learner and his abilities (Muhammad, 1993, p. 14).

The curriculum focuses on translating educational goals into situations and experiences that students interact with to learn and help raise the efficiency and effectiveness of educators by understanding the different forces affecting the formulation and construction of the curriculum, knowing the goals and how to derive them from their sources, and standing on the foundations and criteria used in selecting experiences and content that are presented to students in Any academic level and in determining the appropriate teaching methods (Mohammed, 1991, p. 14).

Given the importance of curricula in the educational process and the role of those curricula in building generations and consolidating the values that societies desire for their generations, education began in the last stages to focus on the school curriculum in a way that enhances its position and role.

In view of the concepts dictated by progressive philosophies regarding the curriculum and its development, the progressive trends in philosophy emphasized that education and its objectives should be in line with the evolving and continuous life. There is no fixed curriculum that is always rigid and responds to changes without a review and development, and the development process must be preceded by an evaluation process for the curriculum in order to know the success of the curriculum in achieving the goals set for it, and this includes

identifying the positive and negative aspects in this regard as a stepping stone towards review and development of all aspects of the curriculum. (Al-Laqani, 1995, pp. 7-8).

The school curriculum, in order to play its role in preparing generations for life, must be in line with the scientific and technical variables that occur in it, help them adapt to it, and be flexible and capable of development on the basis of educational plans that are consistent with the plans of the state (Bahri, 1985, p. 77).

Muhammad (1991) emphasized that philosophies of a progressive tendency see that the goals of education change with changing life circumstances in which education is the important means for individuals to adapt to life (Muhammad, 1991, p. 104).

The textbook is a translation of the curriculum and an application of modern educational methods. The nature of its content and the characteristics of its knowledge structure represent the levels, objectives and concepts that are sound from both an educational and educational point of view, and therefore educators care about it and guide the learners. (Radwan, 1987, p. 182). It is an important tool of education in an era characterized by the progress of knowledge and science in every field of life, which made it an essential pillar of progress and development. (Teardrop, 1982, pp. 64-67).

Proceeding from the importance of education and its role in contemporary life and given the importance of the curriculum and the book and their role in the educational process, the importance of the evaluation process stems from the importance of education, the curriculum and the book. And the importance of evaluation has been evident in the field of education, because the decisions adopted in this field have great effects that are reflected on the generations and then on the whole society, especially that education in this century faces many challenges represented by the nature of the age and what is characterized by scientific progress, population growth and global openness Which necessitates permanent revision and modification in the elements of the educational process, including the textbook (Al-Bassam, 1986, p. 1), (Bahri, 1985, p. 2-3).

Evaluation is an accompanying process of the educational process and the means by which it reveals the extent of success it is achieving in achieving its goals. (Mohammed, 1991, p. 258).

Therefore, we had to conduct examinations of this reality for textbooks and to clarify the positive and negative aspects in it in order to develop it so that it can keep pace with the development taking place in life and perform the required role of the curriculum and the book as it should.

The importance of the research can be seen from the following aspects:

- 1- The reality of textbooks in general is a reason for the low quality of education and poor outcomes, and for dropout and other forms of educational waste.
- 2- The modernity of textbooks in light of the rapid developments in the field of education, and whether they meet the needs of students and the needs of society.
- 3- The continuous need for evaluation as a means of developing science curricula in general due to the importance of these books and their being the backbone on which the educational process depends and the process of providing the student with experiences, skills and information related to technology, mathematics, and mental processes
- 4- Knowing the opinion of mathematics teachers on the extent to which the mathematics curriculum in the intermediate stage is keeping pace with the developments taking place and the extent to which the concepts contained therein are appropriate for the student's age stage.

Thus, the research problem can be determined by evaluating the content of the first part of the mathematics book from the teachers' point of view

The aim of the research:

The current research aims to: Evaluate the mathematics textbook, part 1, for the first grade, intermediate, from the point of view of teachers

Limitations of the research:

The current research was limited to:-

- 1- Math book for the first intermediate grade, part one. Dr.. Amir Abdul Majeed Jassim, d. Tariq Shaaban Rajab and others. 4th floor, General Directorate of Curricula, 2019.
- 2- Faculty members of mathematics for the first intermediate grade in middle schools in the holy city of Karbala governorate for the academic year 2021-2022

Define terms:

1- Calendar

Melhem (2000) defines it as “the process of preparing or planning information that is useful in forming or forming judgments that are used in making a better decision out of multiple alternatives.” (Melhem, 2000, p. 41).

Al-Sadiq (2001) defined it as “a basic part of the educational process that includes three successive processes: measurement, evaluation, diagnosis, and treatment.” (Al-Sadiq, 2001, p. 222).

The procedural definition of the calendar:

It is the judgment issued by the faculty members on the extent to which the evaluation criteria set by the researcher have been achieved

search tool.

2- Mathematics book for first grade intermediate

Procedural definition: It is one of the elements of the curriculum in the middle school, which includes four chapters: integers, rational numbers, polynomials, and open sentences.

3- First intermediate grade:

It is the first academic level out of the three levels of middle school in Iraq, in which the student receives general teaching for various branches of science and knowledge.

Previous studies

1- Study (Al-Shami, 2000):

(Evaluation of mathematics curricula for the first four grades in the basic education stage in the Republic of Yemen)

Objective of the study: The study aimed to evaluate the mathematics curricula for the first four grades of basic education in the Republic of Yemen. By answering the following questions:-

- 1- What are the criteria for evaluating mathematics curricula for the first four grades of basic education?
- 2- To what extent are these standards achieved in the mentioned mathematics curricula?
- 3- What is the achievement level of students in the four grades of basic education in mathematics?

Limitations of the study:

The study was limited to:

- 1- Mathematics curricula for the first four grades of basic education in Yemen.
- 2- Mathematics teachers for the first four grades, administrators, supervisors and specialists.
- 3- Schools of the Capital Municipality, Sana'a.

Study sample:

The study sample included:

- 1- (13) primary schools, including (3) private schools.
- 2- (1040) male and female students from the first to the fourth grade were given an achievement test.
- 3- (70) Mathematics teacher and teacher studying in the first four grades of basic education. (26) administrators, (25) supervisors, (25) specialists in curricula.

Study tool:

The researcher used the following tools:

- 1- Achievement tests for the first four grades of basic education. Each class test consists of (25) questions.
- 2- A questionnaire to find out the opinions of teachers, administrators, educational supervisors and specialists in educational curricula. It contained 147 paragraphs covering six areas.

Statistical means:

The researcher used: **percentage, weightedmean, Pearsoncorrelationcoefficient, percentileweight, analysisofvariance, andstatisticalmeans** for his research.

The most important results

A- Positive aspects.

- 1- Most of the objectives are clear and specific and link the scientific material with environmental issues.
- 2- Some goals are realistic and achievable.

B- Negative aspects.

- 1- General weakness in performing the four arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division).
- 2- Difficulties in arranging numbers in ascending and descending order, especially numbers consisting of three or more places.
- 3- Difficulty writing regular and decimal fractions in the third and fourth grades.
- 4- Difficulties in applying the laws to find the perimeter and area of shapes for fourth-grade students.
- 5- Poor qualification of teachers at the required level and lack of training courses.
- 6- Weak vertical and horizontal integration in the content of the curriculum and textbooks, especially for the books of the first grades in the basic education stage.

The most important recommendations

- 1- Giving each teacher a guide (a guide) to direct the appropriate activities and define the role of the teacher and the learner.
- 2 - The necessity of linking goals to reality and taking into account the individual differences between students in terms of abilities and tendencies.
- 3- Diversity in the use of teaching methods and different activities in line with the topic of the lesson.
- 4- The necessity of using different assessment methods appropriate to the level of students in the first stage of basic education.

The most important suggestions

- 1- Preparing a study on evaluating sports curricula for other stages.
- 2- Preparing a study on the methods of teaching mathematics for the basic education stage.
- 3- Preparing a study on evaluation methods used in basic education.

(Al-Shami, 2000, p. a-z)

2- Study (Al-Qaisi, 2001): (Assessment of the physics textbook for the second intermediate grade from the teachers' point of view).

Objective of the study:

The study aims to evaluate the physics textbook for the second intermediate grade from the teachers' point of view.

Limitations of the study:

The study was limited to:

1- Male and female teachers who teach physics textbooks in middle schools in Karkh and Rusafa districts in Baghdad.

2- The following guidelines as criteria for evaluating the book.

A- The suitability of the scientific material of the book to the level of the students.

B- Pictures and illustrations in terms of their clarity, modernity, and their relevance to the level of students.

Study sample:

The study sample included:

1- All physics teachers in secondary schools in the directorates of general education for the city of Baghdad on both sides of Karkh and Rusafa for the academic year (2000/2001), and the size of the basic sample was (68) male and female teachers.

2- Intermediate schools in Al-Karkh and Al-Rasafa sectors in Baghdad.

Study tool:

The researcher used a questionnaire as a tool for data collection, and it includes two questions divided into two areas:

1- The scientific material of the book.

2- Pictures and illustrations.

Statistical means:

The researcher used: Pearson correlation coefficient, weighted mean, and statistical means for her research.

The most important results**A-Positive aspects.**

First: the scientific material of the book

1- The scientific material in the Physics book has taken into account the level of mental maturity of the students, their interests and tendencies, and was characterized by accuracy, taking into account the gradual organization of the topics from easy to difficult.

2- The scientific material was characterized by its novelty, coherence and non-repetition, as it took into account individual differences.

Second: Pictures and illustrations

1- It is sufficient and varied in its content, characterized by modernity, and is directly related to the subject and its connection with the students' environment.

B-Negative aspects.

First: the scientific material of the book

1- The scientific material does not contain an element of suspense.

2- The scientific material is not related to the Iraqi students' environment.

Second: Pictures and illustrations

1- The images and illustrations do not enrich the content with sufficient information.

The most important recommendations

1- Attention to increase the examples and drawings that are related to the Iraqi student environment.

2- Paying attention to the selection of images and illustrations so that they contain an element of suspense, and enrich the content with sufficient information.

The most important suggestions

1- Conducting an evaluation study of the pictures and illustrations in the physics book for the third intermediate grade.

- 2- Conducting an evaluation study for the two physics textbooks in the second and third intermediate grades in light of their development of students' scientific attitudes and tendencies. (Al-Qaisi, 2001, pp. 14-19)

Chapter III

Search procedures :

1-The research community: the research community consisted of teachers of mathematics, part one, for the first intermediate class, in the center of the holy city of Karbala, who continued to serve for the academic year 2021-2022.

2-Research sample: The research sample consisted of 20 teachers who were chosen randomly.

3-The researcher's tool: the research tool is a questionnaire consisting of 24 items prepared by the researcher through his review of previous studies in the required specialization, and it is part of the descriptive approach prepared for this study.. Appendix (1)

4- Honesty :- For the purpose of verifying the validity of the research tool, the researcher relied on the apparent honesty in this, as he presented the questionnaire to a court sample of specialists in the field of psychology and methods of teaching science and methods of teaching social sciences, Annex No. (2). The researcher took (80%) or more as a criterion for accepting the paragraphs of the questionnaire. (Awda. 1998 p. 275) and they all obtained this percentage and more.

5- Stability: The researcher relied on the method of repetition to verify the stability of the questionnaire, as the researcher presented the questionnaire to an exploratory sample consisting of (10) teachers of mathematics, part 1 in the Karbala governorate center, and after 15 days, the tool was re-presented to them and by extracting the Pearson correlation coefficient, the reliability rate was 82% It is an appropriate value for the research (Odeh 1998, p. 345), and the questionnaire became in its final form, Supplement No. (1)

6- Application of the research: The researcher applied the questionnaire to the basic sample of mathematics teachers, part 1. The application was carried out on 3-4-2022.

7- Correction of the research tool: For the purpose of statistically analyzing the data, the response of the sample members to the questionnaire items was transformed into numbers that can be processed statistically. Grades (3) agree, (2) somewhat agree, (1) I do not agree. So that the degree of the total questionnaire was confined between (24-72).

8- Statistical methods: The researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

the fourth chapter

Presentation and discussion of the results:

First: Presentation of the results:

With regard to the aim of the research, which is to evaluate the mathematics book for the first grade average c1 from the point of view of teachers, the researcher used the weighted mean to determine the severity of each paragraph and the percentage weight for the paragraph of the questionnaire.) or more arbitrator for the accepted paragraph and then rearranged it again according to its severity and as shown in the table.

Table (1) Paragraph intensity, item weight, and the new order of the questionnaire items from the teachers' point of view

original order	Percentile weigh	paragra ph sharpness	Paragraph	T
13	%93	2.81	The end-of-semester questions measure all the cognitive objectives mentioned in the chapter	1
8	%87	2.63	The questions are clear and scientific	2
9	%87	2.63	Examples from the book help the student to solve the exercises	3
12	%87	2.63	The book's presentation style emphasizes the importance of mathematics and the beauty of its topics	4
15	%87	2.63	The method of solving the exercises in the book stimulates the student's thinking	5
16	%87	2.63	The book promotes self-learning for the student	6
17	%93	2.8	The content of the book motivates the student to explore	7
19	%93	2.8	The content of the book is proportional to the number of	8

			lessons offered per week	
1	%81	2.45	The curriculum can be implemented on time for the school year	9
4	%81	2.45	The introduction gives an overview of the book's content	10
5	%81	2.45	The book is distinguished by the modernity of the scientific material and its practical applications	11
7	%81	2.45	The style of the book develops the mental abilities of the student	12
11	%81	2.45	The style of the book ranges from easy to difficult	13
14	%81	2.45	There is a link between the activities, the means, and the scientific material of the book	14
18	%81	2.45	The examples in the book are sufficient	15
20	%81	2.45	The suggested activities can be carried out within the class time	16
22	%81	2.45	It is difficult to explain the topic of square and cube root to the student	17
6	%69	2.09	The teacher can easily communicate the idea of solving the exercises in the book	18
10	%69	2.09	The exercises for each topic are sufficient to review the various ideas and methods	19
21	%69	2,09	I find it difficult to explain and estimate the percentage	20
23	%69	2,09	The book is good in terms of binding and printing	21
24	%69	2,09	The topic of profit and proportional division is easy for the student	22
3	%63		The shape of the outer cover is attractive to the student's interest	23
2	%53		The concepts are clear and appropriate to the cognitive level of the student	24

It is clear from Table No. (1) that the teachers' comments were mostly positive towards the mathematics book C1 for the first average, except for the following paragraphs: Where most of the teachers found that the shape of the outer cover is not attractive to the student's interest, and therefore the concerned authorities should search for another form to attract the students' attention as well. The concepts included in the book are above the student's cognitive level as he finds it difficult to understand them from their point of view. Paragraph (2,3). The results of the research also indicate that the subject of the percentage and its estimation, the teacher finds it difficult to explain it to the student. Therefore, the specialized educational supervision should include teachers in strengthening courses on this topic, paragraph (21) of the questionnaire. Paragraph (3) related to end-of-semester questions received the highest support.

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